

Democracy as Performance: Can Deliberation Survive the Politics of Spectacle?

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1. Introduction

In a world saturated by images and spectacles. Democracy is increasingly unfolding as a performance rather than a practice of collective reasoning. The democratic endeavor has long been tied to the promise of deliberation; the idea that legitimacy arises when citizens freely exchange arguments, exposing power to the discipline of reason.

Jürgen Habermas (1989) has encapsulated this ideal in his conception of the public sphere. The viability of this ideal is being eroded as a consequence of publicity and public performance. This transformation brings up the question: *Can deliberative democracy survive under conditions of performance politics?*

To address this, I start by reconstructing the theoretical underpinnings of the public sphere and tracing how mass media challenged Habermas's notion of rational debate. Then I turn to deliberative democracy as a corrective, emphasizing its normative commitment to communication and transparency (Dahlgren, 2000). Using Parkinson's (2005) criticism as a guide, I contend that contemporary media infrastructures, far from being neutral, actively shape public discourse by narrowing the range of perspectives available for genuine debate through dramatization and exclusion.

Building on this framework, the paper then examines how deliberative ideals are systematically eroded through three mechanisms. First, digital virality and algorithmic manipulation distort equality of participation (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024). Second, market logics that commodify journalism, transforming rational-critical publicity into a staged resource for elites (Chomsky, 1997; Arambala, 2023). And last, the spectacularization and aestheticization of politics displace argument with image, reducing leaders to brands and political programs to symbols (Ortiz et al., 2023).

Lastly, I discuss the politics of visibility, where recognition itself becomes a form of political capital (Thompson, 1990). And how Populism, understood as performance (Petrović Lotina, 2021), is nowadays generated through affective staging. And as a case study, I explore Charlie Kirk, whose political persona was maintained via orchestrated virality.

By combining theoretical critique and empirical illustration. My paper argues that performance politics fundamentally challenges the communicative core of democracy. The following analysis seeks to explore the mechanisms of this erosion, while raising a broader question of whether deliberative democracy can resist the logic of the spectacle.

2. The Public Sphere and Deliberative Ideals

The foundation of democracy is built upon the ideal of a public sphere, where citizens are allowed to freely engage in rational and critical political debate. This concept, as famously described by

philosopher Jürgen Habermas, frames the public sphere as a “realm” that must be accessible to all citizens, giving space for public opinion to be formed (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.47). However, this very sphere is nowadays being co-opted by media manipulation and a focus on performance, which necessitates an examination of whether deliberative democracy can withstand the forces of spectacle.

My approach to this topic starts by tracing Habermas’s conception of the public sphere as a space for rational and critical debate, and how it transformed under the pressures of mass media. As a corrective ideal, I turn to deliberative democracy, highlighting its dedication to communication and transparency. And to polish my argument, I draw upon the scholarship of Dahlgreen and Parkinson to demonstrate how media conditions subvert deliberative ideas by privileging dramatization and strategic dialogue.

2.1. The Transformation of the Public Sphere

Initially, Habermas theorized the public sphere as a space rooted in print culture, where individuals could engage in rational discussion and political debate. However, the sphere's existence is fundamentally tied to a broader range of media, including newspapers, magazines, radio, and television (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 49). Over time, these means of media that initially served as channels for rational, logical, and critical political debate evolved into what critics started calling “pseudo-public sphere” (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.14). This concept suggests a shift away from authentic public discourse towards a more superficial, commodified form of communication, lacking the genuine critical engagement that characterizes a true public sphere. This is known as the "refeudalization of the public sphere".

The critical function of publicity was to expose domination to the “public use of reason” (Habermas, 1989, p.196). But the sphere gradually got hollowed out, as public authority got into competition with publicity. And publicity shifted from being a rational, critical matter to an issue of display, transforming arguments into symbols (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.69).

According to Habermas, the public sphere is compromised. Appearances and representation outweigh reasoned discussion and rational debate, turning politics into a managed spectacle, in which leaders and parties routinely seek the celebratory approval of the depoliticized populace (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.63). In favor of this staged display, arguments are transmuted into symbols, stripping publicity of its critical function (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.69). As a result, the public transforms into spectators consuming symbolic performances, rather than deliberating citizens.

The mass media has diminished the "deprivatized province of interiority", resulting in a pseudo-public sphere that serves as a "superfamilial zone of familiarity" (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 64). This problem cannot be resolved by market logics nor by state broadcasting, as "neither allows for the emergence of a critical public sphere" (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 79).

The public sphere has been significantly impacted by the mass media. Habermas referred to modern publicity as the downfall of rational and critical debate, arguing that elections are no longer the result of disagreements within an institutionally protected public sphere (Habermas, 1989, p.212). Instead, the electorate has been fragmented within the framework of a manufactured public sphere, as the mass media serves primarily as a vehicle for advertising (Habermas, 1989, p.217).

Livingstone and Lunt (1994, p.14) note that the media creates a pseudo-public sphere to divert people's attention from political action, functioning as a space for public relations and passive spectatorship rather than genuine public discourse. The refeudalization of politics and the public sphere turns them into a managed performance, thereby creating a theatrical shift (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 63). Proactively producing an environment conducive to acclamation, fostering an opinion climate rather than genuine public opinion (Habermas, 1989, p. 218).

As the public sphere is increasingly shaped by display and acclamation, deliberative democracy emerges as a theoretical response. This analysis will be extended in the next chapter, where I examine how deliberation seeks to preserve communicative rationality under the shadow of performance politics.

2.2. Deliberative Democracy in the Shadow of Performance Politics

Deliberative democracy emerged from the critique that underlines the importance of open communication within the political sphere, and sees the free exchange of ideas as a crucial component of democracy (Dahlgren, 2000, p. 40). The deliberative model distinguishes between strategic goal-oriented and manipulative action and communicative effort that seeks mutual understanding, trust, and shared knowledge (Dahlgren, 2000, p.40).

Habermas (1996) later expanded this into discourse theory, suggesting that the decisions formed through undistorted communication are the source of legitimacy. However, the social conditions necessary for a functioning democracy are frequently missing in modern media. Parkinson (2005, p.176) warns that the media's capacity to foster rational discourse hinges on the open exchange of ideas, which nowadays is compromised due to the narrow range of issues and perspectives offered. He contends that media dramatization prioritizes the easily narrated and sensationalized viewpoints and excludes the less dramatic ones (Parkinson, 2005, p.183). This dynamic ultimately erodes deliberative ideals, paving the way for the rise of performance politics.

Both inclusive participation and rational critical discourse are necessary for a deliberative democracy, yet contemporary conditions undercut both. The communicative foundation is being eroded as the system prioritizes strategic and instrumental rationality over interpersonal communication (Dahlgren, 2000, p. 40). Hence, the collapse of the communicative network of a public composed of rationally debating private citizens (Habermas, 1989, p. 248). This collapse is not inevitable, as Habermas himself says, rational debate and undistorted communication are possible, and language may yet

escape institutional control (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 70). However, such spaces require "self-organized public spheres", which are also susceptible to social control (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 71).

Deliberative democracy cannot passively depend on the existing communication infrastructures, as the media are not neutral transmitters of information (Parkinson, 2005, p. 177). The next step, therefore, is to investigate how media infrastructures themselves contribute to this erosion, particularly through mechanisms of manipulation that manufacture consent and hollow out rational-critical debate.

3. Media manipulation and the erosion of deliberative ideals

Critical democratic theory repeatedly addresses the idea that the media shapes public opinion rather than simply reflecting it. Arambala (2023) argues that "mass media today appears to be no longer the medium for reproducing public opinion. It has formed part of the structures that manipulate and manufacture public opinion". Similarly, Chomsky (1997) insists that "propaganda is to a democracy what the bludgeon is to a totalitarian state", emphasizing how modern democracies use media systems to "manufacture consent" rather than promoting genuine public reasoning.

The erosion of deliberative democracy by media manipulation can be mapped across three dimensions. On the digital level, virality and algorithmic manipulation function as tools of manufactured opinion. On the institutional level, market logics drive journalism away from its critical function and toward managed publicity. And on the cultural level, politics is spectacularized and aestheticized, recasting leaders as performers and citizens as spectators. In the following three chapters of my work, I will examine each of these dimensions to demonstrate how contemporary media systems transform the public sphere from a forum of debate into a spectacle of influence.

3.1. Virality & Digital Distortion

The logics of virality and algorithmic manipulation are central forces reshaping the political discourse in the contemporary media landscape. While social media platforms were once tools of democratic inclusion, the emergence of manipulative virality has subverted their potential. As Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo (2024, p.90) explain, "Manipulative virality refers to the engineered spread of content to ensure its rapid and widespread dissemination online... constituting a form of deception of public opinion". The viral spread of information is no longer an organic reflection of public discourse, but a carefully orchestrated, professionally planned activity that puts visibility above reason.

Central to this process is the use of bots, fake accounts, and paid buzzers. This undermines the equality of voices, which is essential to deliberative democracy. Bots give a sense of widespread support, creating an illusion of consensus, privileging manufactured opinion over genuine civic

participation (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, p.91). This algorithmic distortion disrupts the deliberative norm of equal participation by adopting a hierarchy of amplified voices.

The economic dimension of virality further compounds these risks. By using bot networks and armies of buzzers, wealthy actors disproportionately acquire influence over these platforms. The result is the systemic privileging of financial power over rational argumentation, eroding the epistemic and participatory ideals that deliberative democracy is founded on (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, pp.92–93).

These dynamics are not simply structural; they are becoming increasingly more intertwined with platform ownership and governance. Elon Musk's acquisition of X (formerly Twitter) illustrates how the political inclinations of powerful individuals collide with the logic of manipulative virality. X's algorithmic modifications after Musk's 2024 endorsement of Donald Trump disproportionately elevated conservative voices, illustrating how platform design can be recalibrated to favor specific ideological currents (Huszár et al., 2021; The Verge, 2024). Implying that this disparity is systemic rather than incidental, Manipulative virality serves only those who can afford digital campaigns to consolidate their influence at the expense of marginalized groups (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, p.92).

Platforms value exposure and visibility over deliberative quality. Bots and hoaxes pass as legitimate indicators of public interest. Algorithms normalize this degraded form of political communication and normalise the misleading discourse by boosting manipulated content (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, p.93). The deceptive use of these tools intensifies this erosion. Fake accounts often created using fictitious identities and images, infiltrate online debates and spread false information, undermining the trust in the veracity of interlocutors (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, p.93). Hoaxes, for instance, are intentional attempts to influence public opinion, relying more on emotional manipulation. These practices replace rational and critical debate with misinformation, weakening the epistemic foundations of deliberative democracy (Widyatama, Ananda & Wiratmo, 2024, p.93).

Taken together, these dynamics reveal how the ideals of deliberative democracy are being hollowed out by algorithmic manipulation. Rewarding sensationalism and misinformation, and privileging artificial voices over rational human, authentic argumentation. Manipulative virality has the potential to transform the digital public sphere into a theatre of influence.

3.2. Market Logics and the Decline of Journalistic Rationality

The role of journalism in sustaining democratic life has always been tied to its ability to promote logical and critical discourse. The Habermasian school views journalism as a cornerstone of the public sphere where citizens deliberate about common concerns (Habermas, 1989, p. 30). Habermas (1989, p.195) argued that modern publicity no longer serves its original purpose of exposing political authority to rational-critical debate. He contended that instead, it has been transformed into a managed

spectacle, functioning as a form of performance. News events now serve as an "engineered stage-managed resource for elites to construct favorable images" (Habermas, 1989, p. 197). The term that Habermas uses for this is "opinion management," which "invades the process of 'public opinion' by systematically creating news events or exploiting events that attract attention" (Habermas, 1989, p. 197). This turns public attention into a product to be consumed, packaged to cultivate, and, preferably, end public debate.

Livingstone and Lunt (1994, p.52) expand on Habermas's critique, arguing that "Party politics and the manipulation of the mass media have resulted in a 'refeudalization' of the public sphere, where representation and appearances outweigh rational debate". They claim that the commodification of news turns public discourse into a staged performance, stripping publicity of its essential function and turning arguments into symbols that demand identification and that reject rational, logical response (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p.64). This trajectory of thought is further confirmed by Chomsky's (1997, pp. 3–7) argument that propaganda is the democratic counterpart of coercion in authoritarian regimes. For Chomsky, media control guarantees that citizens remain spectators, with their consent being manufactured rather than freely given.

Arambala (2023) provides a complementary perspective by describing how the free press itself has become an instrument of manipulation. Mass media creates a structure that manufactures consent by instilling false consciousness to create passive citizens who produce no public opinion and no rational exchange (Arambala, 2023, pp. 17). In this view, journalism is profoundly linked to the commodification of publicity and the consolidation of elite control (Arambala, 2023, pp. 27).

The commercialization of journalism produces specific pathologies that directly erode rationality. Dahlgren (2000, p. 313) notes that journalism increasingly loses its claim to reason, as public discourse degenerates into public relations. The expansion of commercial imperatives pressures for profit maximization, which leads to sensationalism, trivialization, and the prioritisation of entertainment over reasoned debate (Dahlgren, 2000, p. 315). This transformation is rooted in the structural dominance of market imperatives, leading to a situation where the logic of commercialism increasingly shapes media operations and diminishes the space of rationality (Dahlgren, 2000, p. 315).

3.3. The spectacularization and aestheticization of politics

John Parkinson (2005, p. 184) provides a concrete description of how these dynamics unfold in real-world situations. Media outlets favor dramaturgical forms of communication, which are designed to heighten conflict and symbolic reasoning. This logic, he contends, sacrifices complexity and nuance, as the grey zones and the technical and moral complexities of issues are subordinated to the demands of media spectacle. Therefore, what reaches audiences are fragments that have been reconstructed into entertainment and not a depiction of deliberation (Parkinson, 2005, p. 187). He observes that media institutions do not work on transmitting political deliberation, but reshape

political deliberation into dramaturgical forms designed to heighten conflict and symbolic reasoning (Parkinson, 2005, p.178).

The transformation of journalism into a spectacle parallels the emergence of advertising logic in political communication. Ortiz et al. (2023, P.331) argue that advertising prioritizes representational pictures over substantive ideas, turning the political process into a spectacle. These strategies deplete the cognitive resources of audiences, thereby undermining collective rationality and favoring visual frameworks that require less critical scrutiny (Ortiz et al., 2023, p. 332). Thus, the political ideology is easily substituted by the ideology of appearance (Ortiz et al., 2023, p.333). Ortiz et al. (2023, p. 329) further contend that advertising reduces political debate to schematic and superficial forms, where the physical image of the candidate becomes a substitute for thought. The spectacularization of politics through advertising thus transforms candidates into brands, eroding rational debate and replacing political programs with aestheticized images designed to evoke strong and effective emotions.

The theoretical implications of aestheticization are substantial for the existence of deliberative democracy. Squires (1999, p.126) identifies a strand of “aestheticist politics” that accentuates expressive, performative, and bodily dimensions of political life, often through defiance or transgression. Such forms of politics, however, provide only a tenuous basis for collective emancipation and social justice, since they make no claims to universal validity (Squires, 1999, pp.127, 139). The logic of visibility and surveillance is closely linked to the spectacularization of politics. Thompson (1990, p.16) argues that “politics is inseparable from the art of managing visibility”. Connors (2008, p.63) further stresses that spectacle is always a political act that stages power dynamics between spectators, participants, and audiences. More recently, Reinhardt (2023, p.823) highlighted the entanglement of spectacle and surveillance, as state and corporate actors increasingly control the dissemination and circulation of images, shaping public perceptions in ways that extend domination across the visual field.

The preceding analysis has demonstrated how the deliberative foundations of democracy are systematically eroded by media manipulation, market logics, and the spectacularization of politics. What emerges is a sphere shaped by propaganda, commodified publicity, and dramaturgical display. Yet the consequences of this transformation extend beyond the distortion of information and decline of journalistic rationality. Performance politics transform democratic legitimacy by transforming visibility into a type of political capital. To understand how authority, influence, and recognition are now distributed in the public sphere, it is necessary to turn from the critique of manipulation to the analysis of visibility. What will be further discussed in detail in the subsequent section of this work.

4. The Politics of Visibility

The relationship between politics and visibility has become increasingly central in contemporary democracies. With the rise of mass communication and the logic of media spectacle, visibility has

become a form of political capital that determines who gains legitimacy, influence, and authority in public life. This chapter develops this argument by examining the link between the politics of visibility and the erosion of deliberative ideals. This chapter approaches visibility as a decisive currency of political life. My argument is structured around three main points. First, I analyse populism as performance. Second, I situate visibility as a form of political capital, tracing its historical roots and its contemporary intensification through media and advertising logics. Finally, I turn to a case study of Charlie Kirk, whose life and death illustrate the intersection of visibility, performance, and virality as a function of mediated populism.

4.1. Populism as Performance

The rise of populism in contemporary politics has increasingly been understood as more than a set of ideological claims; Petrović Lotina (2021) emphasises that populism functions as a choreographic practice, assembling diverse social forces into a collective identity that is positioned against elites. Benjamin Moffitt (2016) has argued that populism should be understood foremost as a political style: “a political style that is performed, embodied and enacted across a variety of political and cultural contexts” (cited in Petrović Lotina, 2021, p.8). This view decenters ideology and highlights the communicative, affective, and symbolic dimensions of populist politics. Ordinariness, sincerity, and hostility are enacted by leaders in ways audiences recognise and find compelling.

Petrović Lotina (2021, p.12) advances this analysis by framing populism as a “performative practice of constructing the people on the symbolic level”. Populism, in this view, is less about mobilizing existing constituencies. And more about the choreographed practice of bringing disparate grievances, identities, and democratic demands into a single unified collective. His “choreography of articulation” inscribes “the people within a particular symbolic order and embodies a collective will” (Petrović Lotina, 2021, p.12).

This framing implies that populism operates by staging collectivity. It choreographed antagonism between "the people" and "the elite" into emotive power and symbolic solidarity. Leaders act as charismatic conduits, embodying the will of the people and re-creating the state through performance (Marino, 2018, p.17). His everyday populist performance rests on ordinariness as a political claim. The “people” are not an intrinsic entity but a “performed subjectivity” (Kissas, 2022, p.2770). Stories of injustice and victimisation, repeated in personalised formats, enable individuals to appear as authentic representatives of common suffering (Kissas, 2022, pp.2770–2771). In this approach, populism turns everyday life into a political weapon by exploiting the mediatised environment’s demands for affect, visibility, and self-representation.

4.2. Visibility as Capital in Media Democracy

The political function of visibility is not exclusive to the contemporary era. In the Roman Republic, politics was deeply ingrained in a “culture of seeing and being seen” (Flower, 2006, p.322). Public recognition, often through rituals of spectacle such as triumphs or funerals, was seen to be the true measure of authority (Flower, 2006, p.324).

As John B. Thompson argues, “in the era of mass communication, politics is inseparable from the art of managing visibility” (Thompson, 1990, p.16). Visibility is no longer a neutral byproduct of media distribution. It is seen as a resource that political actors must cultivate and control. For politicians, this visibility brings both opportunity and risk: Although it can offer the potential to reach vast audiences and strengthen symbolic authority. It also exposes them to new risks, as “an impromptu remark or an emotional outburst can bring about the fall of an aspiring leader” (Thompson, 1990, p.17).

Visibility in modern democracies is mediated by intricate media ecosystems rather than being limited to actual crowds. For public opinion to exert influence, it must be visible (Lang & Lang, 1983, as cited in Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, pp.92–93). However, this visibility is manufactured under structural constraints that privilege spectacle over rational discourse. As Livingstone and Lunt (1994, p.94) note, “reason reveals itself to be what it really is: a show, a spectacle in which truth is not a content... but a device, an alibi, to get excitement going”

Advertising strategies exacerbate this dynamic by commodifying visibility. Ortiz et al. (2023, p.329) argue that advertising can transform the political process into a spectacle, where the represented image becomes the primary influence on social relationships. In this framework, the candidate’s physical image acts as a label, serving as a substitute for genuine thought. The authors go further to say that the ideology of appearance poses a significant threat, as it has the potential to completely displace political ideology (Ortiz et al., 2023, p.333).

The rise of social media platforms has further intensified the value of visibility as capital. Social media's virality and interconnection created a communication ecosystem where public actors are exposed to an ever-increasing degree of visibility (Kissas, 2022, p.2769). Charlie Kirk exemplifies this transformation, having turned his media platforms into an apparatus of engineered visibility, whose political persona was carefully constructed through digital platforms; his role in this process will be explored in the following chapter.

4.3. Charlie Kirk’s Death and the Media Logic of Populism

As I am writing this paper, the death of the right-wing populist Charlie Kirk has recently been announced. His sudden assassination on 10 September 2025 during a public appearance in Utah has been transformed into a national media event. Political figures and news organizations have turned his untimely death into a symbolic legacy (AP News, 2025; ABC News, 2025; People, 2025). In the following section of this paper, I will examine Kirk as a figure of performance politics: first by

considering what he represented and the communicative strategies that underpinned his influence, and then by reflecting on what his death means for the media environment and the trajectory of public debate.

Charlie Kirk, the founder of Turning Point USA, stands out as a quintessential example of contemporary performance politics. His political influence was rooted in the deliberate use of media platforms and the strategic use of engineered virality and symbolic identity construction (BBC News, 2025). In his life, Kirk was a master of visibility, and in his death, his persona will likely continue to circulate as a symbol within the performative dynamics of American politics.

Kirk's success was built on what Widyatama, Ananda, and Wiratmo (2024, p.85) describe as manipulative virality. The engineered spread of content to guarantee the widespread dissemination online, which they frame as a "form of deception of public opinion" (Widyatama, Ananda, and Wiratmo 2024, p.85). This dynamism is best exemplified by Turning Point USA's network of memes, video clips, and amplified soundbites, as well as the goal of generating outrage and visibility. Kirk's infrastructure amplified certain voices at the expense of others, which made his presence disproportionately loud in the digital sphere.

Drawing from historical precedents, his death will not terminate this structure, but will only leave behind a ready-made archive of engineered virality that will more than likely be repurposed to maintain his symbolic relevance. Fox News portrayed Kirk's passing as a "dark moment for America," with his voice growing "bigger, grander" after his passing (Fox News 2025). At their core, Charlie Kirk's politics were a populist performance.

Following Petrović Lotina's (2021, p.12), "populism is a performative practice of constructing the people on the symbolic level". Kirk continuously positioned himself as the spokesperson for "ordinary Americans" against liberal academia elites (Mayer, 2017). His approach was beyond simple policy argumentation; his strategy involved the symbolic construction of "the people" through a carefully staged rhetorical performance. Petrović Lotina (2021, p.17) further notes that populist performance is built through cultural and political arrangements that move through a charismatic leader. Arambala (2023, p.25) describes public opinion as staged opinion created by experts and mediated by mass media propaganda to maintain control. Such staged opinions circulate widely, disregarding genuine deliberation.

Propaganda is defined to be to a democracy what the bludgeon is to a totalitarian state (Chomsky, 1997, p.29). Kirk's symbolic afterlife will be one of propaganda rather than discourse, where his image serves as a mobilizing instrument. This became evident in the immediate aftermath of his death. Kirk's passing turned into a nationally publicized staged event after Trump's Truth Social announcement and on-camera eulogies.

Trump announced: "*The Great, and even Legendary, Charlie Kirk, is dead... No one understood or had the Heart of the Youth... better than Charlie*" (Trump 2025). At the Pentagon 9/11 ceremony, Trump referred to Kirk as "a giant of his generation", promising a posthumous Presidential Medal of

Freedom (Kile 2025). Here, the politics of visibility merges with what Habermas diagnosed as acclamation politics (Habermas, 1989, p.218). Elite cues, ceremonial honors, and media repetition created a staged opinion that circulates as a symbol rather than an argument, precisely what Livingstone and Lunt (1994, p.63) refer to as the refeudalization of publicity.

5. Conclusion

Taken together, the analysis presented in this work demonstrates how the promise of deliberative democracy has been systematically hollowed out under the conditions of performance politics. Beginning with Habermas's conception of the public sphere, we saw how rational-critical debate was envisioned as the foundation of democratic legitimacy. And how the sphere was brittle from its very origin and increasingly vulnerable to refeudalization

As this work has argued, the shift from deliberation to performance marks a structural transformation of democratic life. Manipulative virality (3.1) prioritizes manufactured consensus and artificial voices over equal participation; citizens become publicity consumers as a result of market-driven journalism (3.2). Leaders become brands and politics becomes entertainment as a result of the spectacularization and aestheticization of politics (3.3), replacing arguments with pictures. Together, these dynamics hollow out the communicative ideals upon which deliberative democracy rests.

Performance politics distorts information and redefines legitimacy, and visibility, as explored in the final chapter (4), turns into a form of political capital. This dynamic can be observed in the case of Charlie Kirk, whose political identity was sustained through engineered virality, and even his death was staged into a spectacle of acclamation, demonstrating how performance now shapes both political life and afterlife. In light of this, we can now answer the question: Can deliberative democracy survive the politics of spectacle?

The evidence presented in my paper suggests that deliberation cannot thrive in the existing environment. Yet, the deliberative ideal should not be dismissed as obsolete. The idea of "self-organized publics" in which language might escape institutional control was one that Habermas explored (Livingstone & Lunt, 1994, p. 70). The survival of deliberation depends on building alternative media ecologies, redistributing visibility as a democratic right, and fostering spaces where rational-critical debate is not drowned out by virality and aestheticization.

In conclusion, deliberative democracy can only survive if it is actively defended and reimagined. It requires institutional reforms and cultural and communicative shifts that prioritize argument over acclamation and participation over spectatorship. To deliberate is to recognize one another as equals, and deliberation may yet survive if such a reorientation can be achieved. Ultimately, the survival of democracy is determined by our collective action and our response to the conditions we have discussed.

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Erklärung zur Prüfungsleistung

1. **Name, Vorname:** Hayaty soundousse

2. **Matrikelnummer:** 8545137

3. **Studiengang:** politikswissenschaft

4.

5. Die am FB03 gültige Definition von Plagiaten ist mir vertraut und verständlich:

6. „Eine am FB03 eingereichte Arbeit wird als Plagiat identifiziert, wenn in ihr nachweislich fremdes geistiges Eigentum ohne Kennzeichnung verwendet wird und dadurch dessen Urheberschaft suggeriert oder behauptet wird. Das geistige Eigentum kann ganze Texte, Textteile, Formulierungen, Ideen, Argumente, Abbildungen, Tabellen oder Daten umfassen und muss als geistiges Eigentum der Urheberin/des Urhebers gekennzeichnet sein. Diese Kennzeichnungspflicht gilt auch für alle Internet-Quellen sowie für Inhalte, die aus eigenen Qualifikationsarbeiten übernommen wurden, unabhängig davon, ob diese als bestanden bewertet wurden oder nicht. Sofern eingereichte Arbeiten die Kennzeichnung vorsätzlich unterlassen, provozieren sie einen Irrtum bei denjenigen, welche die Arbeit bewerten und erfüllen somit den Tatbestand der Täuschung.“

7. Ich versichere hiermit, dass ich die eingereichte Arbeit mit dem Titel Democracy as Performance: Can Deliberation Survive the Politics of Spectacle?

8. nach den Regeln guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis angefertigt habe. Alle Stellen, die wörtlich oder sinngemäß aus Veröffentlichungen oder aus anderen fremden Mitteilungen (inkl. Internet-Quellen und KI-Software) entnommen wurden, sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die vorliegende Arbeit ist von mir selbständig und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel verfasst worden. Ich bin mir bewusst, dass die Nutzung maschinell generierter Texte keine Garantie für die Qualität von Inhalten und Text gewährleistet. Ich versichere daher, dass ich mich textgenerierender KI-Tools lediglich als Hilfsmittel bedient habe und in der vorliegenden Arbeit mein gestalterischer Einfluss überwiegt. Des Weiteren versichere ich, sämtliche Textpassagen, die unter Zuhilfenahme KI-gestützter Programme verfasst wurden, entsprechend gekennzeichnet sowie mit einem Hinweis auf das verwendete KI-gestützte Programm versehen zu haben. Ich versichere, dass ich keine KI-Schreibwerkzeuge verwendet habe, deren Nutzung der Prüfer/die Prüferin explizit schriftlich ausgeschlossen hat. Ebenfalls versichere ich, dass diese Arbeit (auch nicht Teile davon) noch in keinem anderen Modul oder Studiengang als Prüfungsleistung vorgelegt wurde.

9. Mir ist bekannt, dass Plagiate auf Grundlage der Studien- und Prüfungsordnung im Prüfungsamt dokumentiert und vom Prüfungsausschuss sanktioniert werden. Diese Sanktionen können neben dem Nichtbestehen der Prüfungsleistung weitreichende Folgen bis hin zum Ausschluss von der Erbringung weiterer Prüfungsleistungen für mich haben.

10.

11.

12. Frankfurt Am Main

12.09.2025

Soundousse Hayaty

13.

14. Ort, Datum, Unterschrift

15. Diese Erklärung ist der Prüfungsleistung als Anhang beizufügen. Prüfungsleistungen ohne diese Erklärung werden nicht zur Bewertung angenommen.